

Data Management Plan

DSS SS20 UE1

Contact person

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Common DSW Knowledge Model, 2.0.1 (dsw:root:2.0.1)

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Abstract

This experiment is concerned with the automatic detection of spam (i.e. unwanted/pernicious) text messages. It is based on a fully labelled dataset consisting of a little over 5000 text messages from various sources. The data is transformed such that it is more suitable for machine learning approaches, and then used to create a sequential neural network model using Keras with a Tensorflow backend. After training the final accuracy score and loss value are presented, alongside graphs that show their change over the course of model fitting.

Section A: Data Collection

1. What data will you collect or create?

Re-used datasets

We will use the following already existing non-reference datasets:

- **Kaggle source data**

We will download or get a copy.

Data formats and types

We will be using the following data formats and types:

- **CSV Dialect Description Format**

It is a standardized format. This is a suitable format for long-term archiving. We will have only a small amount of data stored in this format.

- **Portable Network Graphics**

It is a standardized format. This is a suitable format for long-term archiving. We will have only a small amount of data stored in this format.

- **Rich Text Format**

It is a standardized format. This is a suitable format for long-term archiving. We will have only a small amount of data stored in this format.

2. How will the data be collected or created?

There will be no instrument dataset in this project.

Storage and file conventions

We will use a filesystem with files and folders with the following folder conventions:

- There will be a **(sub)folder for each step in the analysis workflow**. Each of those will use the following conventions: outputs/results are stored in a folder named "results".

Moreover, we have made appointments about naming the files.

We will not be storing data in an "object store" system.

We will not use a relational database system to store project data.

We will not use a graph database for data in the project.

We will not be storing data in a triple store.

Section B: Documentation and Meta-data

3. What documentation and meta-data will accompany the data?

List of data to be published is given in Section E, Question 9. This also includes information about catalogs where the data can be found. Information about data types used is given in Section A, Question 1.

We will use an electronic lab notebook to make sure that there is good provenance of the data analysis.

Section C: Ethics and Legal Compliance

4. How will you manage any ethical issues?

Data we reuse

- **Kaggle source data** – the existing consent covers our reuse.

5. How will you manage copyright and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) issues?

We will be working with the philosophy *as open as possible* for our data.

All of our data can become completely open immediately.

For the reference and non-reference data sets that we reuse, conditions are as follows:

- **Kaggle source data** – available under specific restrictions, which we will follow in our project.

Section D: Storage and Backup

6. How will the data be stored and backed up during the research?

Data that project members themselves store adequately backed up and traceable. Therefore data are protected against both equipment failure and human error.

7. How will you manage access and security?

Project members will not store data or software on computers in the lab or external hard drives connected to those computers. They will not carry data with them (e.g. on laptops, USB sticks, or other external media). All data centers where project data is stored carry sufficient certifications. All project web services addressed via secure http (https://...). Project members have been instructed about both generic and specific risks to the project.

The risk of information loss in the project or organization is acceptably low. The possible impact to the project or organization if information is leaked is small. The risk of information vandalism in the project or organization is acceptably low.

All personal data will be collected anonymously.

Section E: Selection and Preservation

8. Which data are of long-term value and should be retained, shared, and/or preserved?

We plan to publish the following datasets:

- **Text message input dataset** – This data set will be kept available as long as technically possible.
- **Input data after preprocessing (tokenization and vectorization)** – This data set will be kept available as long as technically possible.
- **Experiment output data** – This data set will be kept available as long as technically possible.

9. What is the longterm preservation plan for the dataset?

- **Text message input dataset** will be stored in a domain-specific repository: [Kaggle Datasets](#). We don't need to contact the repository because it is a routine for us.

- **Input data after preprocessing (tokenization and vectorization)** will be stored in a domain-specific repository: [GitHub](#). We don't need to contact the repository because it is a routine for us.
- **Experiment output data** will be stored in a domain-specific repository: [GitHub](#). We don't need to contact the repository because it is a routine for us.

None of the used repositories charge for their services.

We have a reserved budget for the time and effort it will take to prepare the data for publication.

Section F: Data Sharing

10. How will you share the data?

- **Text message input dataset** – available under some restrictions, which we will follow in our project: Adherence to the Kaggle terms of service as the data isn't generated or collected by us: <https://www.kaggle.com/terms>. Re-users will be able to get access through a specialized process: The data is publicly available for download. The conditions will be published as part of open metadata. The DOI for this data set is <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3757819>.
- **Input data after preprocessing (tokenization and vectorization) i.e. intermediary data** – freely available with obligation to quote the source (e.g. CC-BY). The DOI for this dataset is <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3758037>
- **Experiment output data** – freely available with obligation to quote the source (e.g. CC-BY). The DOI for this data is <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3758323>
- **Code** – code is freely available via GitHub under <https://github.com/jjnp/dss20-ue1> , and can also be accessed via Zenodo under the DOI <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3758024>

Information about used repositories (i.e. where will potential users find out about the data) is provided in Section E, Question 9.

Embargo on the data is described in Section C, Question 5, and Section F, Question 11.

11. Are any restrictions on data sharing required?

Ethical and legal restrictions are documented under Section C. We have used the Data Stewardship Wizard, which made us aware of options to minimize the restrictions.

No data sharing agreement will be required.

Section G: Responsibilities and Resources

12. Who will be responsible for data management?

Jacob Palecek is responsible for implementing the DMP, and ensuring it is reviewed and revised.

13. What resources will you require to deliver your plan?

To execute the DMP, no additional specialist expertise is required.

We do not require any hardware or software in addition to what is usually available in the institute.

Charges applied by data repositories (if any) are mentioned already in Section E, Question 9.